

**THE INFLUENCE OF CORPORATE RISK AND CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AGAINST TAX AVOIDANCE BY SIZE, PROFITABILITY, AND LEVERAGE IT AS A CONTROL VARIABLE
(Case Study In Company registered in JII 2011-2015)**

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ABSTRACT

The revenue generated by our country the majority of the taxes. At the moment there are many companies that have been in Indonesia which will certainly have an effect on taxes. The existence of the company tax revenue will certainly increase. However, if these companies do tax evasion, then tax revenues would be reduced. So in this study, will examine the companies listed on the JII (the Jakarta Islamic Index), more companies prioritize sharia. Surely if the company put forward the sharia they will pay taxes based on rules.

The purpose of this research is to find out and analyze the effect of partially variable and simultaneous corporate risk and corporate governance toward tax evasion with size, profitability, and leverage as control variable at company registered in JII. The population of this research is all companies listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) in 2011-2015. Sampling using a purposive sampling. This study uses secondary data in the form of annual reports and financial data of the company obtained from the official website of IDX or at the official website of the company. From the results obtained that corporate risk and corporate governance as well as size, profitability, and leverage do not have significant influence towards tax avoidance.

KEYWORDS: Corporate Risk, Corporate Governance, Tax avoidance Size, Profitability, and Leverage

INTRODUCTION

Development is an activity carried out by the Government with the goal of creating a just and prosperous society; there have been many changes and improvements made through the reform. But the political and macro economic indicators, Indonesia also has not shown the data encouraging. Then, the role of taxes as the State Treasury again sued! State revenue amounting to RP 1,822.5 trillion, taxes are the main source of State revenue, year 2016 revenues from tax of 74.63% (\$ 1,360.1 trillion), the value of 52.63% VAT and VAT luxury goods of Non oil and gas. The biggest tax revenue from VAT and Vat luxury goods come from companies (taxable employers), which has achieved a turnover of at least 4.8 billion

(Law No 42 Yrs. 2008). From these data there is the possibility of companies in carrying out the duty taxes do not comply with existing legislation. This is in tune with the analysis of tax revenues by Directorate General of taxes (Ramadan, 2015), which show within the last 5 years (2009-2014), Indonesia's tax ratio never moved from 11-13%. Low tax ratio can be meant as a sign of the magnitude of the GDP was still able to spend freely by communities without tax withheld. In other words, the low tax ratio of a country can be interpreted that the condition of a country's taxation is still underdeveloped. Based on IMF data in 2011, Indonesia's tax ratio potential should be 21.5%. But that year, Indonesia's tax ratio only reached 11.77%, there is a huge potential loss of (21.5% -11.77%) ie

9.73% or if converted to rupiah, then his potential loss amounting to 723 trillion. If the company tries to take action by reporting payment of taxes less than properly, in order for the company's profit to be more optimal, and the action taken has the aim of reducing taxable profit through tax planning both tax avoidance and tax evasion then called tax aggressive (Martini, 2012; , 2014; Suadijaya, et al., 2015). The weakness of the tax regulation makes the emergence of tax aggressive. This can arise from actions taken by the management or owner of the company. In addition to the corporate risk, companies go public in Indonesia are also required to apply corporate governance. Corporate governance describes the relationship between the owner and the Manager of the company in determining the direction of the performance company called corporate governance. The implementation of corporate governance aims to minimize agency conflict. The agency conflict arises when the objectives to be achieved by the manager of the company are not in line with the interests of shareholders. The alignment of shareholder relationships and corporate managers will influence the tax policy to be used. While in companies listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index are based on the provisions of Sharia, certainly puts more tax evasion will be trying to avoid.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Agency Theory

The existence of separation of ownership by principal by controlling by agent in a company tends to cause agency problem between them (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). The shareholders as the financiers want to get the most profit for their investment, while the management authorized to manage the company is assumed to want to get high financial compensation from the company. The desire to maximize the welfare of each is what sometimes causes management to take company policies that are not in line with the interests of shareholders resulting in agency problems. Agency theory appears to address agency problems.

Tax Avoidance

Hutagaol (2007) categorizes the differences in financial engineering as tax evasion or tax avoidance, ie whether financial engineering made by the Taxpayer is contrary to the applicable taxation provisions or not. If contrary to the provisions of taxation, the tax savings measures are classified as tax evasion. If it is not contrary to the prevailing tax regulation then the action is included in the category of tax avoidance (tax evasion). However, in practice it is not as simple as classifying it, because the difference between tax evasion and tax evasion is very thin. So it could happen that the original financial engineering intended by the Taxpayer to avoid taxes but

unconsciously he has done tax evasion. According to Masripah, et al (2015) the essence of tax evasion is all the act of minimizing tax debt legitimate to do, as long as not regulated in detail in tax invitation invitation. The purpose of tax avoidance is to minimize or minimize the amount of tax payable.

Corporate risk and Tax avoidance measures (aggressive tax)

The Executive in a company has two characters in the exercise of his duties, i.e. risk takers and risk averse (Low, 2006). The leader of the company with a risk taker character tend to be more courageous in making decisions even if the decision is high risk, as they are motivated to earn higher profit levels (Dewi, 2013). Therefore they will continue to strive to bring a high cash flow to meet the goals of the company owner. The action of aggressive tax aims to reduce taxable profit, reducing tax payments and cash flow can improve eventually entered the company. This increase in cash flow can increase the incentives that executives will receive from shareholders.

Dyrenge et. al. (2010) examines the effect of Top Executive individuals on corporate tax evasion. By taking samples as many as 908 leaders of companies listed in ExecuComp obtained the result that the leadership of the company individually has a significant role to the level of tax avoidance.

Corporate Governance and Tax Avoidance Measures (Aggressive Tax)

The implementation of good corporate governance is expected to increase transparency in financial reporting, in accordance with the basic principles of corporate governance itself. High transparency can balance the amount of information owned by the management and owners, as well as other parties with an interest in the company. The existence of this information balance can certainly reduce the existing agency conflicts within the company, such as aggressive tax action. This can happen because with a balanced amount of information, an opportunity for the management to take aggressive tax action can be reduced by a higher level of supervision through quality information. Desai and Dharmapala (2006) research is an example of empirical research showing the effect of corporate governance on tax evasion. Desai and Dharmapala (2006) using the company data contained in Compustat database (1993-2002 period) have examined the effect of corporate governance practices on the relationship between management compensation / incentives and tax avoidance measures. This study was conducted by dividing the sample into two groups (well governed companies and poorly governed companies) based on the level of corporate governance practices of each company. The results show that the effect of management's compensation / incentives on tax

avoidance measures differs between firms that have good corporate governance practices and those with poor corporate governance practices. The relationship between management compensation / incentives and tax avoidance measures has a negative effect on firms with poor corporate governance practices.

Size, Profitability and Leverage against Tax Avoidance Measures

The size of the firm (size), profitability, and leverage as the control variables in this study also have a role in affecting the cash effective tax rate (CETR) (aggressive tax action proxy). According to Rego (2003) in Dewi (2013) large companies have greater likelihood to take aggressive tax action because it has more complex business activities. ROA is a ratio that describes the company's ability to generate profits. High ROA causes tax payments to be made by the company will also increase, so the CETR becomes higher (Prakosa, 2014). Leverage is the ratio of corporate debt. Mulyani's research, et al. (2014) states that high leverage will result in high interest expenses, resulting in lower tax payments, which impact on CETR decline. Similarly, Suardijaya, et al (2015) and Masripah, et al (2015) used control variables (Size, Profitability / ROA, and Leverage) to determine their effect on tax avoidance measures.

Islamic perspective

From the above discussion states that all the sample companies in JII do not apply tax avoidance. Although tax is not an obligation in Islam but in Surah An-Nisa: 59 states that we as a faithful people must obey Ulil Amri or government:

الرسل وأطيعوا الله وأطيعوا أمروا الذين أوتوا منها ما الله إلى ف ردوه شيء في ت نازعتم ف إن منكم الأمر وأولي خير ذلك الآخر وال يوم با لله تؤمنون ك نتم إن والرسل ت أوي لا وأحسن

59. " Hi folks who believe, obey Allah and obey the Messenger (His), and ulil amri among you. Then if you differ on the opinion of something, then return it to Allah (Al-Qur'an) and the Messenger (sunnah), if you really believe in God and the next day. That is more important (for you) and better consequence. "Although tax is not an obligation but taxes are beneficial to the benefit of the nation. Ulil amri or the government may levy taxes on its people for as long as it is for the benefit and welfare of the nation and not for the benefit of the individual or any particular group.

METHODS

The existence of separation of ownership by principal by controlling by agent in a company tends to cause agency problem between them (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). The shareholders as the financiers want to get the most profit for their investment, while the management authorized to manage the company is assumed to want to get high financial compensation from the company. The desire to maximize the welfare of each is what

sometimes causes management to take company policies that are not in line with the interests of shareholders resulting in agency problems. Agency theory appears to address agency problems.

DISCUSSION

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Model	Unstandardize d		Standardize d		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1 (Constant)	-1.027	1.405		-0.731	.505
KomInd	.789	.597	.545	1.322	.257
KomAud	-.102	.041	-.626	-2.494	.067
KIns	.490	.407	.486	1.204	.295
RISK	.575	1.441	.284	.399	.710
SIZE	.061	.038	.425	1.611	.182
ROA	2.726	1.948	.982	1.400	.234
DER	-.501	.290	-.669	-1.731	.159

a. Dependent Variable: TA

Source: primary data, processed (2017)

$$Y = -1,027 + 0,789\text{KomInd} - 0,102\text{KomAud} + 0,490\text{KIns} + 0,575\text{RISK} + 0,061\text{SIZE} + 2,726\text{ROA} - 0,501\text{DER} + e$$

Audit Quality Variable is issued in this research because it has the same value in each period, so it can not be processed.

The Influence of Corporate Risk Against Tax Avoidance

From the results of multiple linear regression test above that shows the value of regression coefficient of 0.575 and has a significance value of 0.710 means that corporate risk variables have a positive and insignificant effect on the variable tax avoidance, hypothesis h1 rejected. Corporate risk in the management company has two characters namely risk taker or risk averse. Management that chooses high risk action ie risk taker causes corporate risk is also high, most likely to tax avoidance. While management who choose the action with low risk of risk averse prefer to sacrifice expected benefits, in this case avoid

taxes. Corporate risk in this study measured by the standard deviation of EBIT divided by total assets did not affect the tax evasion of companies registered in JII. This is indicated because the value of corporate risk does not show a small number in other words the executives are more risk averse than risk takers. Risk averse managers prefer relatively low risk and are willing to sacrifice some of the expected benefits of reducing variation in outcomes (March and Shapira 1987). This study is not in line with research by Suardijaya et al (2015) which states that corporate risk has a negative and significant.

The Influence of Corporate Governance on Tax Avoidance

From the results of multiple linear regression test above corporate governance is proxied through 4 components namely, Independent Commissioner, Audit Committee, Institutional Ownership, and Audit Quality. Quality Audit is issued in this study because it has the same data value in each period, so it can not be processed.

Independent Commissioner shows the value of regression coefficient of 0.789 and a significance value of 0.257 means the Independent Commissioner variable has a positive and insignificant influence on the variable tax avoidance. This is indicated because most companies still have a proportion of independent commissioners less than half the proportion of the board of commissioners. So the supervision of the board is less than the maximum, causing the independent commissioner to pay less attention to the tax problem.

Audit Committee shows the value of regression coefficient of -0.102 and significance value of 0.067 means that the Audit Committee variables have a negative and insignificant influence on tax avoidance variables. It is possible that the average number of audit committees is relatively the same.

Institutional ownership shows the regression coefficient value of 0.490 and the significance value of 0.295 means that the Institutional Ownership variable has a positive and insignificant influence on the tax avoidance variable. This is indicated because most institutions prefer to pay attention to the institution itself rather than the ownership of its shares in a company. This is fair because the institution itself does not want its institutions to suffer losses and perhaps the ownership of shares of an institution in a company only as an additional income from the institution itself and institutional ownership entrust the board of commissioners in terms of supervision so that the ownership of the institution is not so concerned with the policies created by the management company. In addition, institutional ownership may not be able to control the

management of the company so that the institutional owner does not pay much attention to whether the company does earnings management or not.

From the above results, it can be concluded that Corporate Governance has no significant effect on tax evasion. This research is not in line with Desai and Dharmapala (2006) research, Sartori (2009) which shows the result of corporate governance has a significant effect on tax evasion.

Influence Size, ROA and Leverage Against Tax Avoidance Size

From result of regression test show result that size have positive and not significant effect. Despite the size of the company that is not small scale, has total assets or total assets of the company, the stock market value and the number of sales are not small which indicates the greater the size of the company, the greater the tax to be paid. However, in the test results of companies listing in JII was not doing tax evasion.

ROA

From result of regression test show result that ROA have positive and not significant effect. Companies on average have a positive level of profitability but do not take aggressive tax action, it is possible companies do earnings management so can not know the actual profit.

Leverage

From result of regression test show that leverage have positive and not significant to tax avoidance. This shows that leverage will not increase the company's tendency to tax avoidance, the high leverage value indicates the company's lack of ability to pay its debts which will cause the lower tax payments. The average leverage value of the sample company does not show a high value, this means the company has the ability to pay its debts and cause higher tax payments. But the company chose not to tax avoidance. Due to the existence of government regulations, the tendency to conduct tax evasion will be narrower.

CONCLUSION

From the calculation that has been done, it can be concluded that corporate risk and corporate governance and size, profitability, and leverage have no significant effect on tax avoidance. The sample companies listing on JII do not avoid taxes, in the sense that they are carrying out their tax obligations well. Future research is expected to:

1. Further research can do research by comparing other countries.
2. Adding other variables such as corporate social responsibility and earnings management.
3. Using the data panel panel method.

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